

ZON THE QUESTION OF OSCILLATIONS OF AN ELASTIC-FASTENED HOUSING IN THE DIFFERENCE OF ITS CENTER OF GRAVITY AND THE CENTER OF ELASTICITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14252699>

Abstract. The article deals with vibrations of the body of onboard radio-electronic equipment in the case when its center of gravity is not located above the center of elasticity of the spores. A substantiation of generalizations of coordinates is carried out. A technique is given for elucidating the possibility of "breakdown" of elastic supports. The solution of the problem is carried out in principal coordinates.

Keywords: body vibrations, center of gravity, supports elasticity, oscillations, generalizations of coordinates.

Introduction. Consider the vibrations of the case, the dimensions of which are greater in length than in width. Such a problem can be considered as a flat one [1,2]. Figure 1 shows a diagram of a flexible installation of the body on an oscillating platform.

fig. 1

The center of elasticity is the point of application to the body of the resultant statically unbalanced system of elasticity of the suspension. The coordinates of the center of elasticity in an arbitrarily chosen coordinate system are determined by expressions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x_0' &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i'}{\sum_{i=1}^n c_i} \\
 y_0' &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n c_i y_i'}{\sum_{i=1}^n c_i} \\
 z_0' &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n c_i z_i'}{\sum_{i=1}^n c_i}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here :

x'_0, y'_0, z'_0 - coordinates of the center of elasticity in an arbitrarily chosen coordinate system;

x'_i, y'_i, z'_i - coordinates of fastening to the body of the i-th elastic support in an arbitrarily chosen coordinate system;

c'_i - coefficient of elasticity of the i-th support;

n - number of elastic supports.

It is obvious that the transfer of the origin of coordinates to the center of elasticity leads to the expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i &= 0 \\ \sum_{i=1}^n c_i y_i &= 0 \\ \sum_{i=1}^n c_i z_i &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Here : x_i, y_i, z_i - coordinates of attachment to the body of the i - th support relative to the center of elasticity. In order to be able to use the Lagrange equations of the nth kind in the future, it is necessary to set the movement of the body in generalized coordinates, i.e. mutually independent coordinates that determine the position of the body at any time. Such coordinates independent of each other are the vertical translational displacement of the body together with the center of elasticity and the rotation of the body around the transverse axis passing through the center of elasticity [3,4,5].

Indeed, if only a vertical force is applied to the body, the line of action of which passes through the center of elasticity, then the moment of statically unbalanced elastic forces of the suspension relative to the center of elasticity will be equal to zero:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_0 [c_i (z + \varphi x_i)] = 0$$

or

$$z \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i + \varphi \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i^2 = 0$$

but

$$\sum_i c_i x_i = 0, \quad a \sum_i c_i x_i^2 \neq 0$$

hence

$$\varphi = 0 \tag{3}$$

Thus, in the case of the action of a vertical force, as laid to the center of elasticity, the body will receive only vertical translational movement along with the center of elasticity [6,7].

If, however, only a moment is applied to the body in the vertical plane, then the main vector of statically unbalanced elastic forces of the suspension will be equal to zero:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n c_i (z + \varphi x_i) = 0$$

or

$$z \sum_{i=1}^n c_i + \varphi \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i = 0$$

but

$$\sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i = 0, \quad a \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \neq 0$$

hence

$$z = 0 \tag{4}$$

Thus, in the case of a moment in the vertical plane, the body will only receive rotation around the transverse axis passing through the center of elasticity.

It should be noted that, usually taken as generalized coordinates, vertical translation of the body together with the center of gravity and rotation of the body around the transverse axis passing through the center of gravity, in case of mismatch center of gravity with the center of elasticity, will be interdependent parameters (when one of them changes, the other gets changed) and cannot be used as generalized coordinates.

Indeed, if only a vertical force is applied to the body, the line of action of which passes through the center of gravity, then the moment of statically unbalanced suspension elastic forces relative to the center of gravity will be equal to zero:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n m_c (p_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n m_c \{c_i [z + \varphi(x_i - d)]\} = 0$$

Here d is the horizontal distance between the center of gravity and the center of elasticity.

$$\begin{aligned} & z \sum_{i=1}^n c_i (x_i - d) + \varphi \sum_{i=1}^n c_i (x_i - d)^2 = 0 \\ \text{or } & z \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i - z d \sum_{i=1}^n c_i + \varphi \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i^2 + \varphi d^2 \sum_{i=1}^n c_i - 2\varphi d \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i = 0 \\ & \text{but } \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i = 0, \quad a \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \neq 0 \end{aligned}$$

hence

$$\varphi = - \frac{z d \sum_{i=1}^n c_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n c_i l_i^2 + d^2 \sum_{i=1}^n c_i} \tag{5}$$

Thus, in the case of a vertical force, applied to the center of gravity, the body simultaneously with the vertical translational movement together with the center of gravity by an amount z will receive an angular displacement by an angle φ around the transverse axis passing through the center of gravity.

If only a turning moment in the vertical plane is not applied to the body, then the main vector of statically unbalanced elastic forces must be equal to zero:

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{i=1}^n c_i [z + \varphi(x_i - d)] = 0 \\ \text{or } & z \sum_{i=1}^n c_i + \varphi \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i - \varphi d \sum_{i=1}^n c_i = 0, \end{aligned}$$

but

$$\sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i = 0 \quad , \quad a \sum_{i=1}^n c_i \neq 0$$

hence (6)

$$z = -\varphi d$$

Thus, in the case of action in the vertical plane of the moment, the body simultaneously with angular displacement around the transverse axis passing through the center of gravity, at an angle φ will receive vertical translational movement along with the center of gravity by the amount z .

Based on the foregoing, when the body is elastically installed, when its center of gravity does not coincide with the center of elasticity, the generalized coordinates are the vertical translational movement of the body together with the center of elasticity - z and turning the body at an angle φ around the transverse axis passing through the center of elasticity.

When studying the oscillation of a housing mounted elastically on an oscillating platform (the installation diagram is shown in Fig. 1), we assume that the mass of the installed electronic equipment is significantly less than the mass of the oscillating platform and therefore, the installation of the apparatus will not change the law of platform oscillations [7,8]. Let us take platform vibrations as a certain bag of vertical harmonic vibrations, since for most vehicles on which on-board radio-electronic equipment is installed, $y(t)$ is a superposition of several high-frequency oscillations on the main low-frequency ones.

$$y(t) = \sum_{j=1}^s Y_j \sin p_j t \quad (7)$$

where Y_j and p_j - amplitude and frequency of the j -th harmonic oscillation. The kinetic energy of an oscillating body and the potential energy of its elastic multipoint support, written in generalized coordinates, have the form:

$$\begin{aligned} T &= \frac{1}{2} M \dot{z}^2 + Md \dot{z} \dot{\varphi} + \frac{1}{2} J_0 \dot{\varphi}^2 \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} c_z z^2 + \frac{1}{2} c_\varphi \varphi^2 + \frac{1}{2} c_z y^2(t) - c_z z y(t) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Here:

M - hull weight;

J_0 - moment of inertia of the body about the transverse axis passing through the center of elasticity;

d - abscissa of the center of gravity of the body relative to the center of elasticity;

$c_z = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i$ - coefficient of elasticity of the support for vertical movements of the body;

$c_\varphi = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i x_i^2$ - coefficient of elasticity of the support for angular displacements of the housing.

The kinetic energy of an oscillating body, written in generalized coordinates, contains a term with the product of generalized velocities, as a result of which the differential equations of

the body oscillations will be interconnected [7,8]. Therefore, after passing linear homogeneous coordinate transformation

$$\begin{aligned} z &= \lambda_1 \theta_1 + \lambda_2 \theta_2 \\ \varphi &= \theta_1 + \theta_2 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

let's move on to the so-called principal or normal coordinates θ_1 and θ_2 . It is known that the kinetic energy of the system, written in principal coordinates, does not contain a term with the product of principal velocities, and the potential energy does not contain a term with the product of principal coordinates. Using these provisions, the values of constant coefficients λ_1 and λ_2 determine from the expression

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{1}{2d} \left[(r_c^2 - \rho_{un}^2) \pm \sqrt{(r_c^2 - \rho_{un}^2)^2 + 4d^2 r_c^2} \right] \quad (10)$$

Here:

$$r_c = \sqrt{\frac{c_\varphi}{c_z}} - \text{distribution coefficient of elastic supports;}$$

$\rho_{un} = \sqrt{\frac{J_0}{M}}$ - radius of gyration of the body relative to the transverse axis passing through the center of elasticity.

The kinetic energy of an oscillating body and the potential energy of its elastic support, written in principal coordinates, have the form:

$$\begin{aligned} T &= \frac{1}{2} J_1 \dot{\theta}_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} J_2 \dot{\theta}_2^2 \\ \Pi &= \frac{1}{2} c_1 \theta_1^2 + \frac{1}{2} c_2 \theta_2^2 + \frac{1}{2} c_z y^2(t) - c_z \lambda_1 \theta_1 y(t) - c_z \lambda_2 \theta_2 y(t) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Where

$$J_1 = M \lambda_1^2 + 2Md \lambda_1 + J_0 \quad (12)$$

$$J_2 = M \lambda_2^2 + 2Md \lambda_2 + J_0$$

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 &= c_z (\lambda_1^2 + r_c^2) \\ c_2 &= c_z (\lambda_2^2 + r_c^2) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Using the Lagrange equations of the 2nd kind

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{\theta}_1} \right) - \frac{\partial T}{\partial \theta_1} &= - \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \theta_1} \\ \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{\theta}_2} \right) - \frac{\partial T}{\partial \theta_2} &= - \frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \theta_2} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

we obtain differential equations for body oscillations in principal coordinates

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{\theta}_1 + k_1^2 \theta_1 &= \sum_{j=1}^s h_{1j} \sin p_j t \\ \ddot{\theta}_2 + k_2^2 \theta_2 &= \sum_{j=1}^s h_{2j} \sin p_j t \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where

$$k_1 = \sqrt{\frac{c_1}{J_1}} \quad (16)$$

$$k_2 = \sqrt{\frac{c_2}{J_2}}$$

$$h_{1j} = \frac{c_2 \lambda_1 Y_j}{J_1} \quad (17)$$

$$h_{2j} = \frac{c_2 \lambda_2 Y_j}{J_2}$$

Solution of differential equations (15) (at $\theta_0 = 0$ and $\dot{\theta}_0 = 0$) can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_1 &= \sum_{j=1}^s \frac{h_{1j}}{k_1^2 - p_j^2} \sin p_j t + \sum_{j=1}^s \frac{p_j}{k_1} \frac{h_{1j}}{k_1^2 - p_j^2} \sin k_1 t \\ \theta_2 &= \sum_{j=1}^s \frac{h_{2j}}{k_2^2 - p_j^2} \sin p_j t + \sum_{j=1}^s \frac{p_j}{k_2} \frac{h_{2j}}{k_2^2 - p_j^2} \sin k_2 t \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Angular and vertical body movements determined by generalized coordinates z and φ , we obtain using transformation (10). The deformations of the elastic supports of the body will be equal to

$$\Delta z_i = z + \varphi x_i - y(t) \quad (19)$$

Here x_i - abscissa of the attachment point of the i -th support to the body. If the vibrations of the body are within the limits of displacement of the extreme elastic supports allowed by the limiters, then its vertical and angular acceleration is determined from the expression [9,10,11]:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{z} &= \lambda_1 \ddot{\theta}_1 + \lambda_2 \ddot{\theta}_2 \\ \ddot{\varphi} &= \ddot{\theta}_1 + \ddot{\theta}_2. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Conclusions. However, as soon as the dewarping of one of the extreme elastic elements reaches the value allowed by the displacement limiters of the corresponding element, then there will be a blow to the limiter or the so-called "breakdown" of the elastic support, which is determined mainly by the low-frequency components of the oscillations. Impact accelerations are known to be many times greater than the accelerations of harmonic oscillations. Therefore, the above discussion of the possibility of "breakdown" of the elastic support for given platform vibrations is of practical interest for determining the operating conditions, reliability and durability of the onboard radio-electronic equipment and elastic supports of its body.

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